

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE USAGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article examines the influence of information and communication technologies on the educational process of higher education. Based on the strategic objectives of the Concept of Higher Education Development until 2030, the possibilities of modern forms of educational process organization and digital technologies were analyzed. The purpose of the ideas presented in the article is to effectively use the possibilities of ICT and improve the quality of education.

Key words: higher education, information and communication technologies, digital technologies, quality and efficiency of education, Internet.

Introduction

Today, creating the digital industry of the future requires starting the digital transformation of the country by increasing the level of human capital development, and rapidly digital transformation in education.

Today's classrooms are very different from a decade ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, iPads, tablets, smart boards, and other types of educational technology. As in other parts of the world, the seven-screen generation of the digital generation - TV, computer, tablet, tablet, smartphone and smartwatch - has appeared in Uzbekistan. As a result of having such a dense digital environment and constant interaction with it, the thinking and information processing processes of today's students are fundamentally different from the thinking and information processes of the past. The digital generation cannot and should not be taught the way our parents were taught. Blackboards and white chalks cannot be used to educate this generation. Changing the blackboard to white and the chalk to a marker doesn't change anything, it's not the way to motivate today's students to learn and develop the skills to succeed in the job market.

It is necessary to adapt the educational system to the digital generation by mass and effective use of innovative educational technologies and didactic models based on information and communication technologies. At the same time, it is necessary to actively use the research-based approach in the educational process, and with this, it is possible to develop the skills of students in scientific research and to form their creative abilities and creative thinking based on IT competence. Information and communication technologies are not a solution to all problems in the education system, but a tool for making lectures and seminars informative and interactive for the digital generation. It should also be noted that teachers retain the main role in the interactive learning process focused on the needs of students.

Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 on the approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation - further improvement of electronic educational resources for the higher education system, as well as ensuring the use of domestic and global educational resources [1], dated October 8, 2019 —On approving the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 in Decree No. PF-5847 —introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, individualization based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, webinar, online, "blended learning", "flipped classroom" technologies, and the determination of tasks such as wide implementation[2] requires the implementation of a number of works within this direction.

Literature analysis

Till that date, a number of scientific studies have been carried out on digitizing the higher education system of our country, introducing modern information and communication technologies into the educational process, providing students with modern knowledge, and improving computer literacy. In particular, by Academician S.S. Gulyamov and Associate Professor M. Abdullaev, digitalization of the higher education system, introduction of new directions and disciplines in digital economy technologies, reform of the education system through the use of cloud technologies, effective use of modern methods in teaching, including interactive whiteboards and tablets, artificial intelligence application of technologies[3], the necessity and benefits of using digital technologies in distance education for students, and statistics on the use of distance education are presented, and the use of digital technologies and the need to introduce new generation systems of distance education, it is faster to learn new skills or subject materials through the distance education system, that it is easier and cheaper is described in detail. Also, in our country, research was conducted on the problems that hinder the effective implementation of distance education using digital technologies and their solutions [4].S. A Ilayarova focuses

on the role of information and communication technologies in improving the quality and efficiency of the educational process of higher education in Uzbekistan, the interdependence of information and communication technologies and advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the analysis of the dynamics of the reforms carried out in relation to the promising trends of the field, and the educational process modern forms of organization and possibilities of digital technologies are analyzed [1].

Many problems of traditional education are being solved by distance learning, online courses, mobile and electronic learning resources. It is appropriate to mention the scientific results of some world-renowned scientists and researchers. As a historian of science, education, and technology, David Franklin Noble has explored the possibilities, achievements, and shortcomings of distance education [3].

Another technologist, Bob Johnston, says that any results of science and technology development should not be limited, but should be used effectively [2]. His main idea is that modern education should not hinder young people's interest in IT technologies, but it is necessary to teach them to use these tools rationally. We also support Bob Johnston's approach. Because young people determine their life goals and positions by means of current news and achievements. They created their lives through science.

In the researches of the mentioned authors, it is recognized that positive progress in the implementation of ICT in the educational system is realized through independent education and requires a conscious approach of students to learning and learning a profession. We also support their opinions and emphasize that the presence of any high technology cannot contribute to the education of the necessary person for the era if it is not approached with a conscious (purposeful) approach. People should always keep in mind that information and communication technologies are a means to achieve the goal.

Research methodology

This article covers the comparative analysis of the research conducted in recent years on the implementation of ICT and innovative approaches to the educational system, the identification of problems, the implementation of observations, and the development of scientifically based proposals and recommendations on digital technologies that should be applied to the educational process.

Analysis and results

When it comes to the world experience of using ICT in social structures, since 2005, at the end of every year, the World telecommunication/ICT indicators symposium (WTIS) [2] The Symposium was held for the sixteenth time in 2018 by the World Telecommunication Bureau in Geneva, Switzerland according to which

51.5 percent of the world's population, i.e. 3.9 million people, used the Internet [2], according to which the figures on the application of ICT in the socio-economic sphere in Uzbekistan were studied. The figures show that the possibilities of using ICT in our country are growing, but this growth is much lower than in other developing countries [1]. There are a number of factors that contribute to these metrics not being up to par. Among these, the speed, price and other important features of the Internet in our republic are not at the required level. This is due to financial opportunities, the quality and number of existing material and technical facilities not being able to meet the needs of the population and the requirements of the times. Nevertheless, the introduction, expansion and popularization of ICT in education continues.

According to the researchers, no sector can be as important as education for the development of the state. The concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 envisages the implementation of several measures to introduce digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process [2]. In particular, the issues of individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, wide implementation of webinar, online, "blended learning" and "flipped classroom" technologies [2] were discussed. It is known that "blended learning" and "flipped classroom" technologies are forms of organizing the educational process, which have aspects that shape the student's creative and systematic thinking, ability to make independent decisions, and organize scientific activities. At the same time, these forms of education are based on independent education, which forms the skills of self-organization, continuous development, clearly defining goals, and the ability to see the future. Current trends of development require a person to receive continuous education (Life longing education). For this, a person must be a researcher. Important features of research in the 21st century are shown in the following:

- creating information;
- search for information;
- information sorting;
- assimilation of information.

The correct and appropriate use of the above technologies of "blended learning" and "flipped classroom" serves to form and develop these qualifications and skills of subjects of higher education. These technologies cannot be implemented effectively without ICT. In this regard, ICT competence of professors and students has a special place in higher education.

The development of information and communication technologies has led to the emergence of electronic education. Electronic education (English Electronic Learning, E-Learning for short) means getting an education by means of information

and electronic technologies. UNESCO defines e-learning as follows: E-Learning is learning with the help of the Internet and multimedia.

E-learning includes:

- independent work with electronic materials on TV, DVD, mobile phone, personal computer and other devices;
- get advice, direction and assessment from experts (teachers) who are geographically (regionally) far away by engaging in remote communication;
- creating communities of users of social networks that have started virtual learning activities;
- ability to deliver e-learning materials on time and during the day (standards of e-learning materials, special tools of distance education), etc.

The cited "blended learning" and "flipped classroom" technologies are one of the means of organizing electronic education.

Conclusions and suggestions

In general, expanding the scope of ICT implementation in higher education is the need of the hour. According to world experts, the need for IT specialists will increase in the future. Therefore, in his address to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, the head of our state put forward a proposal to implement the "One million programmers" project. Therefore, we should also try to train skilled personnel who are in high demand by implementing ICT, despite the existing shortcomings and obstacles, without breaking away from world development. Based on the above, we make the following suggestions - in order to keep up with the times in the way of education and vocational training, it is necessary to massively develop the competences of using information and communication technologies in all citizens of our country - to ensure that every family in our republic has at least one laptop. We think it's time for parents to feel their responsibility in carrying out this work.

After all, the investment spent on education and knowledge always pays off;

- effective use of information and communication technologies by exemplary professors and teachers engaged in scientific-pedagogical activities in the higher education system, in particular, supporting their innovative approaches to teaching, creativity, giving them freedom to organize training sessions when such talent is observed, and introducing incentives when high performance is observed;

- based on the internal capabilities of each higher education institution (including branches in remote areas), it is necessary to implement effective methods and means of using information and communication technologies in the organization of the educational process. In this regard, it is appropriate to regularly organize events such as competitions for startups and innovative projects aimed at solving local problems for young researchers and researchers, and organize support for them.

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